

Importance of Effective Business Communication for Promoting and Developing Hospitality Industry in Saudi Arabia A Case Study of Jazan (Jazan)

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ABSTRACT

"A man's beauty is in his tongue" Prophet Muhammad (PBUH).

It is always saying that a communication is a key to success. It is a basic need to make any relation better and persuasive. Communication has power to make and destroy the image in no time. It is seen that communication skill becomes more important than the educational qualification because sometimes people who are less educated but having a good communication skill can win the argument, and can get job and raises, on contrary, a person having better qualification and intelligence but lacking in communication skill, becomes ignored and avoided from the important meetings.

This research aims at casting shadow on effective communication in context of pragmatics understanding. This is a qualitative research, in which data has been collected through questionnaires. Most of the response was collected online from the employees working in different segments Hospitality industry in Jazan region.

KEYWORDS: Business Communication, Hospitality, Tourism, Communication, Hotels, Airlines, Jazan, Gizan, Saudi Arabia

INTRODUCTION

Effective business communication depends on different things in which Semantics, Pragmatics and syntax are the most important factor to have an effect on communication skill. If one of these would be ignored a message can be decoded wrongly. In this paper pragmatic understanding is highlighted to make business communication more effective and successful. In the corporate world, where government and private sectors play many important roles to develop and represent their companies and the country, a lot of deals are finalized on the bases of business communication via phone or personally. A little mistake or ignorance can destroy the image and loss millions of rupees, so pragmatic understanding is much necessary to make a communication successful.

Background to the Study:

Pragmatics contains some important measures to be understood closely to get and give a clear vision about the statements. The first and most important is to use the language for different purposes and in different environment, for example, when someone greets (Hi Hello), for informing (I am going to college now), demanding (Go and bring me a pen), promising (I am going to give you a

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novel you asked), and requesting (please pass this tissue box). Another important thing is hanging the language according to the situation and listener, for example talking to a baby and an adult are different things. There are some rules also which are supposed to be change according to the culture of the listener.

Statement of the Problem:

The main problem of understanding occurs when communication happens between the people of different culture and regions. In this comprehensive age when world is becoming smaller every day, everyone has to deal with different type of people having different cultural background, then it becomes very significant to have knowledge of pragmatics. It is seen that sometime people talk in inapplicable or inappropriate things during their discussing important matter or start talking unrelated things. Most of the time, these problems occur because of the lack of pragmatic understanding. Specifically, while someone is dealing with the people of other cultural background, he/she has to be very much careful about the pragmatics of that language.

Objectives of the study

The research aims at:

1. Opening up new platforms to learn pragmatics in daily life.
2. Developing interest in learning the trend of different traditional cultures to have more successful business communication.
3. To alleviate anxiety for connecting to other regional's and nationals who have different color, language and culture.

Questions of the research

To meet the foregoing stated objectives the following research questions are raised:

1. How can pragmatic understanding be a rich source of having a fruitful business communication?
2. Are the employees of Jazan region aware of the importance of pragmatics?

Research Methodology

Participants

The participants sample selected for this study consisted of employees of different Hotels, Restaurants, Airport employees in Jazan. This study is done among 300 employees and students of different levels. They are selected randomly for this research.

Instrument

The current study used one tool which was questionnaires. Around 250 questionnaires were taken for assessment, which was suitable for eliciting suitable response.

Procedures

Questioners were sent online to different people with proper instructions, and no specific time was assigned for it. We took interviews of few students of different levels studying in Jazan University.

Literature Review

There are many researches which have been done on the same theme, which shows that pragmatics also has an inevitable part to make business successful or failure. Learning only grammar of a new language cannot be enough to understand the language but its cultural background and socio-cultural behavior of people also plays an important role to understand the language. As business world is spreading bilingualism is also increasing day by day, people from business background are learning different languages not because of their interest but this is the demand of the day.

During this research, I encountered a person from Middle East when my wife joined a college of Jazan university in Saudi Arabia, we had language problem. He couldn't understand me, and, I was also new there, so I was also blank

Data Analysis

Data for this research paper was collected online, most of the employees' feedback, which was selected randomly, was attached with examples from their professional life which they experienced while dealing with the people of different cultural background. Firstly, they were asked about their role in organization so that only best concerned people could be contacted for this research paper.

First question, in questionnaire was: **Have you ever deal with the people of different cultural background on behalf of your organization?** In which, 80 percent of people were experienced who dealt with foreigners and also with the people of different region in India, while 20 percent never interact with the people of different cultural background.

for Arabic language. I went to his office to complete the formality of joining and further processing, after giving all documents I was waiting for his response if the supporting documents are enough or not, in return he wave his hands in the air rubbing one hand with another, a strange gesture for me. I could not understand the meaning so I asked him again, "is it enough or do you want more documents of mine" he looked at me in the same manner and again did the same with his hands speaking in Arabic "Ya Allah Rouh" then I got it that his hand are the sign of finishing the work while in our country this waving hands have different meaning, the similar example was coined by Schermerhorn (1993-55), he states that a good business relation can be failed due to the lack of cultural awareness of other region or country you are dealing with. He gives an example of an American Businessman who lost his business because he did not know that facing the shoe towards a Saudi is a sign of disrespect. His second mistake he handed over his documents to that Saudi person with his left hand which is not considered good in Muslim culture.

Businessman, who have to interaction with different nations, should be aware of the new fashion, culture, words of the concerned language, because, sometimes what is polite for you could be considered rude by another culture. There are many issues which are considered very important to know before dealing with different cultural people:

- Time of contact
- How to address

Time is an important factor to make the communication effective, especially, in India, if someone wants to talk about benefits which will increase the income of the organization, early hours of the day will be the best time to discuss, on the contrary if any business executive comes to discuss about the good which company has to pay or debts that is delayed, then it would bring more harshness and negativity to the relationship of two companies. While in middle east if anyone has to talk about any type of financial matters, then early hours of the day are considered good as post lunch period is not very much important for them.

Secondly, the way to address the people is also an important aspect to make business relation successful. Sometimes calling people with their first name and with last name also make a big difference and affect on the business deals. In USA calling people with their first name is considered rude as only close friends and family members can call each other with their first name, while in most places of Asia calling people with their first name is more welcoming and friendly. Like this, these are very minor things which are to be considered important before dealing with different cultural background, otherwise these minor things can spoil the relationship in a while.

Second question: *Do you find any difficulty while dealing with the people of different culture and nations?* Got similar response where 50 percent said yes, they find it difficult to have a formal talk with the people of an unknown cultural background while 50 percent of people were negative about that.

For the third question, when they were asked: *Do you need paraphrase your statements to the listener or people get you at first time when you are dealing with different nationals?* Most of the people were agreed that they need to paraphrase their sentences while dealing with the foreigners, while 30 percent of them were negative about the paraphrasing.

When participants were asked: ***Do you think learning a new language is not enough until and unless you have knowledge of the pragmatics of that language?*** Majority of the people were in favor of understanding of pragmatics of a new language because without pragmatics message could be decoded wrongly, while 15percent of people did not give any importance to pragmatics.

Do you think learning a new language is not enough until and unless you have knowledge of the pragmatics of that language?

Half of the participants were agreed that unknowingly or unconsciously they leave the central topic of discussion and move to another topic while this can spoil a good business deal if something unimportant or irrelevant would be spoken and sometimes this can be inappropriate for other party who has different moral, culture and values. The question was: ***Do you feel sometimes you start unrelated topic during important business communication?*** 50 percent of the participants were well aware about the topics they discuss in the meetings.

Do you feel sometime you start unrelated topic during important business communication?

Do you think some people start a meeting in a disorganized way?

Do you think some people start a meeting in a disorganized way?

After a conversation, do you think that point could be spoken more clearly if you could prepare it before?
6040

After a conversation, do you think the point could be spoken more clearly if you could prepared it before?

Do you think good communication can affect the important decision of the organization?
80%, 15%

Do you think good communication affect the important decision of the organization?

Do you know anything about pragmatics?

Yes 30%

No 70%

Do you think pragmatic understanding is important for good business communication?

Results and Discussion of Findings

Good communication plays a major role for a successful business, then, successful business employment to a lot of educated people and these people make a good harmonious society, furthermore all these societies turn into a good nation. A communication not only need verbal knowledge, but nonverbal knowledge also makes a big difference, in which pragmatics understanding is an unavoidable part of successful business communication.

Conclusion:

To conclude this research, it is analyzed that to understand a new language vocabulary and grammar are not enough, these things only provide with bookish knowledge, but to use that new language its practical use is much more important to understand. Generally, it is seen that books

don't provide us all practical knowledge of a new language as these are reliant on rule and regulation while the language which is used in general speaking is found rather different from the formal language, as a result, It becomes very important for the employees to have the basic knowledge of pragmatics before starting a new business with a person of different culture and nationality.

Major Finding of Research:

It is seen although pragmatics is a very important part of a language but ignored to be taught in classrooms. As an infant baby needs pragmatics understanding while learning a language same thing apply when a learner studies a new language. In Indian context, still half of the people send their children to study in government schools where *Hindi* is a

medium of communication; students always have a hesitation to speak English in front of those students who are from English medium schools. Generally, they are confused to select an appropriate word according to the situation. This lack of pragmatic understanding fills them with negativity. Any communication while its business or nonbusiness is successful while spoken with confidence and clarity always give a good result.

Suggestions and recommendation:

- Pragmatics should be the part of academic syllabus.
- Employees should get training before dealing with the people of different culture and countries.
- Movies and social media are a good source for pragmatic understanding.
- Learner should learn new language with its pragmatics.
- Case study method should be used while teaching the pragmatics understanding.
- Lectures should be arranged for the employees related to the culture and language before sending them to communicate on behalf of an organization.

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